

GENDER APPROACH IN EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AND ITS MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: From the presentation of the educational system to the active solving of problems and the development of specific solutions, from the mastering of individual subjects to the multidisciplinary study of complex life situations, the cooperation of teachers and students in choosing educational content and methods. This transition is associated with a change in value indicators in education. Value indicators of primary education determine personal, social and state orders for the education system expressed in the requirements of the State Education Standard. In this article, one of the important tasks of state orders is the gender approach and its features in teaching foreign languages to elementary school students.

Key words: Educational system, gender approach, primary education, methodology, foreign languages.

Introduction:

At the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries, a new direction appeared in the science of pedagogy - genderology, a science that deals with the consideration of social interaction between men and women based on intergender social tendencies.

The concept of "gender" was taken by local researchers from foreign colleagues in 1980. For the first time, this concept was introduced into the scientific literature by the American educator J. Scott (Joan Scott), to show the differences in the social-role relations of women and men. Modern science distinguishes gender terms. The first was used to show the anatomical and physiological characteristics of people. With the help of these characteristics, all people are divided into men and women. But in addition to the biological differences between the sexes, there are also differences in their social roles, behavior and emotional characteristics. The English word "gender" was borrowed to indicate the social interaction between men and women.

When studying the gender differences of students, it is impossible not to mention such a concept as the teacher's gender competence, which includes:

- informing the teacher about the gender characteristics of girls and boys in raising and teaching children;
- mastering by teachers the organizational, psychological, pedagogical and didactic aspects of managing children's activities, taking into account the child's psychophysiological and individual characteristics, focusing on gender identity.

Almost every teacher pays attention to the differences between boys and girls. These differences should be considered at five levels: genetic, physical, cognitive, psychological, and communication.

Table 1.

Girls	Boys
Differences at the genetic level	
Girls developed the left hemisphere, which is responsible for organizing speech, writing and calculation, intuitive orientation in space, developed clear visual, figurative thinking. Long-term memory is dominant.	In boys, the right hemisphere is dominant, it is responsible for orientation in space, abstract thinking. Working memory and imagination also prevail.
Differences at the physical level	
Girls have less mass, but more grace, flexibility and mobility. Girls quickly develop precision in coordination of movements, they are neat and careful, they have great precision and coordination in movements.	Boys have a larger body weight and greater physical strength, they develop motor skills faster.
Differences in cognitive level	
A quantitative approach to studying educational material prevails in girls, they are distinguished by the clarity of analysis, they are prone to algorithms, templates, and they are distinguished by intuition and caution, analytical approach, and the ability to analyze on an emotional and emotional basis. The level of concentration, unlike boys, is lower.	Boys tend to have a qualitative approach to studying educational material, tend to abstract thinking, creativity and independence. They are distinguished by the pursuit of imagination and philosophy. There are arguments, debates, a desire to gamble. High concentration rate.
Differences at the psychological level	
Adaptation to the environment in girls goes through experience, emotional disturbance. But they tolerate stressful situations more easily by switching to other emotions or tears. Relies more on intuition. They have good short-term memory and good vocabulary. Attention is very well developed.	Boys have a quick reaction to environmental influences, easy adaptation to it. They cannot handle stress.
Communicative component (differences in the level of communication)	
Girls are compassionate, often show affection and care. They are prone to changes and diversity in communication.	Boys are aggressive, often show hardness and toughness, constant in friendship, more determined in their actions, love risk; there is a sharp alternation of activity and passivity.

A student's gender has some influence on school success. Maccoby and Jacklin studied this problem in 1974 and came to the conclusion that girls are superior to boys in verbal skills, while boys achieve great results in working with spatial images. Children's behavior is influenced by different social expectations for boys and girls.

Carol Gilligan found in 1987 that girls who had a balanced and strong sense of personal identity during middle childhood faced significant obstacles in their intellectual development during adolescence and young adulthood.

Negative experiences at school and at home, combined with widespread gender stereotypes, contribute more to the emergence of gender differences in academic achievement than brain physiology.

Boys have a tense relationship with the teacher in primary school: they are often insulted, punished - such pedagogic influences are used that cause negative emotional reactions.

The faster development of the right hemisphere leads to the manifestation of involuntary intuitive reactions in boys, the further development of irrational mental activity, the development of the field of figurative memory and negative emotions, and the increase in aggressiveness of behavior. This contributes to the breakdown of boys' emotional and trusting relationships by teachers in the first years of schooling, which also leaves a mark in later years.

For boys, only a short assessment is not enough, only a broken, clear explanation is effective for them, and positive assessment is especially important. Boys need to understand the meaning and significance of what is required of them.

In such situations, boys try to avoid the pressure of adults, before girls are freed from it. Therefore, indirect requests, instructions, friendly requests are more effective for them. Self-esteem is very important for personality development. It is rarely enough for them. Unstable self-esteem is also common, any luck increases self-confidence, any failure sharply lowers self-esteem and causes an attack of self-doubt. Therefore, it is characteristic for boys: the higher their self-esteem, the more they tend to appreciate other people, forgive their shortcomings, and vice versa, boys' self-esteem. The lower his self-esteem, the worse he thinks about the people around him, the more painfully he experiences their situation.

Thus, the efforts of parents and teachers should be aimed at forming self-esteem in the child.

Brain differences.

Recent brain research shows that there are two major physical differences between male and female brains, as well as how men and women use brain power. First, the corpus callosum, which connects the left and right hemispheres of the brain, is larger in women than in men. Second, the left side of the brain grows more slowly in boys than in girls. This is why boys tend to develop formal language and communication skills later than girls.

Imaging studies show that men and women use brain power in different ways. When performing complex tasks, women tend to use both sides of their brains to solve the problem, while men are more suited to single-tasking.

Although many are skeptical of such notions, neuroscientists generally agree that brain development explains the fundamental differences in the early development of boys and girls, and therefore may be counterproductive. The right hemisphere of the brain develops faster

than the left hemisphere, but there is some reason to believe that the left hemisphere of the brain develops more slowly in boys than in girls.

Conclusion:

Also, girls in the first or second grades have high skin sensitivity, i.e. they are more disturbed by discomfort in the body and respond more to touch and caress.

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